

ROBOTICS WORKSHOPS 3RD YEAR

[Deliverable 2.3]

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ER4STEM - EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS FOR STEM

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1 ROLE, PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVES OF THE DELIVERABLE

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide information about the progress of WP2 “Educational Robotics Workshops”. In this deliverable, we describe the improvements made on the design of the generic curriculum on educational robotics, where we connect the elements and processes, which the ER4STEM team applied to deliver Educational Robotics Workshops (henceforth: ERWs), as well as to present the progress of the delivery of the ERWs. The report provides an update on the process, which will be used for ER4STEM Curriculum description in D2.4. Quantitative data in this deliverable is based on the information reported through the workshop information forms, provided by each partner.

1.2 RELATIONSHIP TO OTHER ER4STEM DELIVERABLES

Draft descriptions of the ER4STEM framework, the criteria for selecting good practices and the Activity Plan template were initially presented in D1.1 Best Practice & Requirements and D4.1 First Version of the Activity Plans. These elements correlate with D1.2 ER4STEM Framework First Structure and Roadmap 2nd Year and D4.2 Operational Release of Activity Plans.

This report provides essential information about the ERWs progress, implementation process and generic curriculum. The generic curriculum and progress indicators are based on the Workshop Information forms and Activity Plans as they were reported in July 2018. More details and analysis on the curriculum content represented by specific Activity Plans will be provided in D4.3 Final Release of Activity Plans.

The educational robotics workshops run alongside the implementation of the D6.2 Evaluation Tool Kit. Data handling follows the data structure defined in D8.1 Data Management Plan. Conclusions in D6.3 Year 1 Evaluation were taken into account when the ERWs implementation process was updated. The workshops reported in this deliverable are evaluated in D6.5 Year 3 Evaluation

The structure of this report follows the already established structure and guidelines in D2.2 Workshop Report 2nd Year.

1.3 STRUCTURE OF THIS DOCUMENT

Section 2 A GENERIC CURRICULUM FOR EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS presents the concept of a generic curriculum. Section 3 Development of a Generic Educational Robotics Curriculum provides sample learning paths and details about how the workshops can be organised as a curriculum and logically, Section 4 ER4STEM Workshops Progress Review represents the status of the workshops, as well as the quantitative indicators for the progress of educational robotics workshops implementation. Section 5

Conclusion / Outlook provides a summary of the conclusions and the next steps to follow for the educational robotics workshops development and continuous improvement.

2 A GENERIC CURRICULUM FOR EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS

Among the core goals of the ER4STEM project, is the aim to develop a generic educational robotics curricula, functioning as a mediating instrument between several of the work packages under the project, and to further ensure the usability of the project's products by a broader community of relevant stakeholders, identified in D1.1 (D1.1 Best Practices and Requirements), including but not limited to **teachers, educators, researchers and academia**.

In order to gradually develop the generic educational robotics curricula during the overall project implementation phase, the ER4STEM project team applied an iterative approach of work. At each step of the development process of the ER4STEM generic curricula for educational robotics, we describe the progress achieved on a yearly basis in the respective workshop reports: D2.1 for year 1, D2.2 for year 2 and D2.3 for Year 3 (the current report). Following this practice, we made sure to be constantly updating and aligning the curriculum to all other work packages and project products on a yearly base. Furthermore, this approach enabled us to discuss the curriculum with relevant stakeholders at different stages of its development, to receive constant feedback, and to be able to iterate and improve the result in each of the project years. The information included in those yearly reports will be summarized and presented as a final version in D2.4 ER4STEM Curricula.

During the course of this process, the implementation team behind the development of the generic educational robotics curriculum had the chance to meet educators and researchers through events like the webinars, conducted under WP5¹ (reported in D5.3 Report on the Repository Workshop). Through such events, educators and other relevant stakeholders were able to openly share their opinion and provide feedback. What we heard on multiple occasions was that teachers would like to have access to educational robotics Activity Plans and teacher content, but plan to later on modify all educational resources to fit their specific context, and plan to use the Activity Plans available within the ER4STEM repository for ideas and guidelines, if they find content that resonates with their general use case (i.e. they want to teach STEM, a certain programming language or an interpersonal skill).

Exactly this need, voiced by relevant stakeholders throughout the ER4STEM project's implementation period, convinced us to focus on the concept of a generic educational robotics curriculum.

Assuming the general definition of curriculum being a general plan for educational activities, Adams and Adams [1] define a curriculum as ***“everything that goes in the learners' life such as planned and not planned interaction of pupils with educational objectives, instructional content, materials and resources used and materials and resources not used, the sequence of courses, objective, standards and interpersonal relationships”***.

Following this definition, the ER4STEM project correspondingly presents the generic educational robotics curriculum in three integrated components: context of generic educational robotics

¹ Conducted on 16th and 22nd of January 2018. For further information, see D5.3 Report of the Repository Workshop

curriculum, content of generic educational robotics curriculum, and generic process for the implementation of the educational robotics activities.

1. Context of the generic educational robotics curriculum

The context of the generic educational robotics curriculum provides the necessary background information for the integrated organization of educational robotics activities. This component is of paramount importance to the adequate development, implementation and evaluation of the educational robotics activities. The context refers to the Framework of the ER4STEM project, which is under development in WP1, and further provides a summarized overview of high level, process, indicators and prerequisites for conducting educational robotics activities under this curriculum. Furthermore, to serve relevant stakeholders, the ER4STEM team will introduce the concepts of a generic educational robotics curriculum map to fit into the context component of the curriculum. The curriculum map is the contextual visualization of educational robotics learning opportunities, as organized content into a set of use cases and contexts, revolving around desired learning outcomes.

2. Content of the generic educational robotics curriculum

To serve the objective of this generic educational robotics curriculum, as initial content, the Activity Plans developed from the partners under the ER4STEM project WP4 will be applied.

The Activity Plans describe in detail (D4.1 First Version of the Activity Plans and [15]) the following key elements of the curricula on a micro (workshop) level:

- Objectives and competencies in the Activity Plans are structured and described under the following categories:
 - Subject-related;
 - Technology use related;
 - Social and action related;
 - Argumentation and fostering of maker-culture;
- Content based on the objectives, target knowledge and skills represented in the Activity Plans as “How to” in the classroom;
- Teaching (instructional) approach and materials are represented in the Activity Plans as Learning procedures section;
- Target participants are described in the “Students” (target audience) section in the Activity Plans;
- Necessary resources – experts, facilities and materials are described in the Social orchestration”; “Space Info” and “Materials and artifacts” sections;
- Final outputs and deliverables are described and evaluated in the “Assessment procedure” section of the Activity Plan.

The ethical and legal aspects regarding the collection of information from the students, the parents, the schools and teachers were considered in detail and taken into account in the assessment procedures (see D6.1 Pre-Kit for Evaluation).

Finally, the industry needs, targeted by the ER4STEM framework, were justified according to societal/industrial needs/demands and forecasts, and were researched and taken under consideration throughout the development of the ER4STEM framework and then introduced within the content of the Activity Plans through the workshops objectives. As an example, during the second project year, we included explicitly 21st century skills in all workshop Activity Plans.

During the final phase of the curriculum development during Year 3 of the ER4STEM project, we introduced **the concept of learning paths (could also be referred to as curriculum paths)**, designed to suggest and visualize to teachers ways to approach their desired learning outcomes through a set of activities.

3. Generic process for the implementation of the educational robotics activities

The need for a generic process for the implementation of educational robotics activities stemmed out of the necessity to describe to a larger community outside the project the sequence of activities involved - initiation, preparation, delivery and finalization. Major organizational steps will be described in 3.3 “Generic Curriculum: Process of the ERW Implementation and Delivery” of the current document and broken down into sets of actions, in order to facilitate the transfer of expertise, acquired throughout this project. This process could serve teachers, researchers, educators and academia as a systematic walkthrough of a successful workshop delivery. In the 3rd year of the project, we updated the process with steps that utilise the new development of the project such as the curriculum map and the already developed ER4STEM repository.

Finally, but yet importantly, this deliverable will present some aggregated results from the data, obtained throughout the third project year. This would serve the curriculum, at this point of its development, as estimated outcomes from its successful implementation and adaptation to a tailored context.

3 DEVELOPMENT OF A GENERIC EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS CURRICULUM

A generic educational robotics curriculum, as understood by the ER4STEM project, is a product aiming to serve as a mediating artifact between the project framework, as under development in WP1, and the implementation of workshops (WP2), integrating products developed in WP4, in alignment with the evaluation results from the workshops (WP6). Key elements of the generic curriculum for educational robotics are included and visually presented within the ER4STEM Repository (repository.er4stem.com) in order to facilitate the navigation and the understanding around the educational robotics Activity Plans, included within the repository. **Overall, a generic curriculum is the combined integrated knowledge about context, content and process as described in the previous chapter.**

Furthermore, a generic curriculum will serve the meso and the macro levels of ICT integration in the classroom, as identified by Wang and Woo [2] - **a) *micro level* where integration of ICT involves a specific lesson, aiming to support student learning in specific concepts b) *meso level*: where integration involves a specific topic and c) *macro level* where integration of ICT happens at the level of a course.**

As discussed in the previous chapter of this report (2. A GENERIC CURRICULUM FOR EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS) the micro level of the curriculum is covered by the Workshop Activity Plan. Therefore, the generic curriculum on educational robotics developed under the ER4STEM project targets the meso and macro levels of ICT integration, with respectively its context and content levels. In order to do that, two concepts were introduced to the development of the curriculum by the implementation team: 1) learning path and 2) curriculum map, which will be presented in detail in 3.1 and 3.2 of this deliverable.

Last but not least, the generic curriculum on educational robotics will support the dissemination of good practices, related to the field of educational robotics in Europe and beyond. The curriculum developed under the ER4STEM project is intended to serve educators, researchers and other relevant stakeholders in the field of educational robotics, to design and develop their own educational activities and initiatives. Our hope is that through this curriculum, we will share our experience and expertise, so that others could benefit from the concepts included in it and could further apply them for their educational or project purposes.

3.1 GENERIC CURRICULUM: CONTEXT

Overview of the Curriculum Context

Regardless of similarities and common elements that the educational robotics learning activities might share, components of those activities might appear fragmented, especially due to the multidisciplinary nature of the field of robotics, STEM and social sciences domains alike. Thusly, the need of a framework, effectively making evident the relations between seemingly distant activities, is required to provide a common baseline for operation with the instrumentarium, data and guidelines, elaborated under the ER4STEM project.

The framework behind the pedagogical approaches applied, or the targeted and estimated outcomes in terms of 21st century skills cultivation, is in fact a wholesome but yet complex structure with the goal to provide generic guidelines on how to understand, create, implement, sustain and evaluate educational constructionist activities within shared, public spaces, through robotics as a mediating artefact to engage and empower children to:

- Engage in collaboration;
- Provide sense of achievement;
- Empower children to develop the ability to recover from failure;
- Provide and involve children in a creative environment;
- Provide children with an environment to cultivate further interests within the domains of science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM);

The framework developed under WP1 is intended to be applied along and prior to the generic educational robotics curriculum, in order to serve as a baseline for the design or adaptation of educational robotics activities. It will furthermore, explain the common ground and the interconnectivity behind the educational content addressed by the activity plans (for detailed information on the content and the Activity Plans, please refer to WP4 Pedagogical Activities, D4.2 Final Release of Activity Plans).

On a macro level, the approach underlying the delivery of the ER4STEM educational robotics activities consists of four main macro steps (**Error! Reference source not found.**): design or adaptation, implementation, evaluation or assessment, and improvement. This aims to suggest that **all activities presented could be adapted to fit a certain context, be it pedagogical, logistical or technological**. The framework behind the ER4STEM project will also aim to guide teachers, researchers and educators towards a generic process for developing and structuring their own educational robotics activity or curriculum. Below, in Figure 1, is presented the macro process definition, as elaborated in D1.3 Towards an Extended Definition of ER4STEM Framework and as shown in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1 ER4STEM Framework's Macro Process Definition (for more information, see D1.3 Towards an Extended Definition of ER4STEM Framework)

The first phase is divided in two possible steps, which represents the possibility to design an activity from scratch or adapt one from other existing activities. The generic educational robotic curriculum developed under WP2 supports this initial step of the macro process of the delivery of educational robotics activity, by assisting teachers, educators, researchers and academia to identify desired learning outcomes within the ER4STEM experience that could serve their purpose and further provide with guidelines for the organization of an activity that might be appropriate to their unique use case.

The second phase of the macro process definition is the implementation phase. Beyond the actual delivery of the activity, the implementation phase, as defined by the ER4STEM Framework, will put a strong emphasis on engaging the students. The generic educational robotics curriculum serves the goals of the implementation layer of the macro process by providing a generic process for the delivery of educational robotics activities (see 3.3 of the current document).

Within the generic curriculum, a set of activities, tested out and assessed within the ER4STEM implementation phase will be organized into structured learning paths (more information in 3.2 of this Deliverable) and will serve to facilitate the first two layers of the ER4STEM Framework's Macro Processes.

The third phase provides instruments and procedures for evaluating the implementation in order to identify the need for future improvements. The fourth and last phase focuses on possible improvements of the Activity Plans based on information derived from the implementation in real settings, reflections from the teachers, students and the designers. Once the activity has been improved, the cycle should be continuing with the adaptation of the activity for future groups and their specific educational context, as necessary. For the last two processes, the curriculum could serve as

provision of general guidelines. The process, described in detail in 3.3 “Generic Curriculum: Process of the ERW Implementation and Delivery” of the current deliverable could be applied in all phases of organization of educational robotics activities.

All of the above-mentioned levels, along with the processes relevant to each level, are supported by a glossary and a skills tree, which are presented in detail in WP1. The aim of both the glossary and the skills tree is to establish a common language between and align relevant stakeholders to the context of the ER4STEM project in general. The skills tree serves to provide an interconnected representation to the skills, targeted by the educational robotics activities.

Last but not least, within the framework, a general understanding of 21st century skills and what they stand for is crucial. Although the set of skills targeted by a set of activities might vary, in WP1’s D1.4 ER4STEM has identified ten values, which were selected based on ER4STEM’s aim and industry requirements. As a result, these values cover some 21st century skills (i.e. Collaboration, critical thinking, communication and critical thinking) and pedagogical aspects (i.e. Pedagogical methodologies, mixed-gender teams, differentiation, multiple entry points, evidence of learning and changing attitudes towards STEM). These values and their definitions are as follow:

1. **Collaboration:** Students must be able to work effectively and respectfully with others. More specifically to a) contribute constructively to project teams b) be helpful and make necessary compromises to accomplish a common goal c) assume shared responsibility and value the individual contributions when working in a team d) use collaborative technologies to connect and work with others (i.e. peers, experts or community members etc.) globally.
1. **Critical thinking:** More specifically to be able to a) use various types of reasoning depending on the situation b) analyze and evaluate major alternative points of views c) synthesize and make connections between information and arguments d) interpret information and draw conclusions based on the best analysis e) reflect critically on learning experiences and processes.
2. **Communication:** Students must be able to communicate with others effectively. This includes the ability to a) articulate thoughts and ideas effectively using oral, written or nonverbal communication skills b) communicate complex ideas clearly and effectively c) publish or present content that customizes the message and medium for their intended audience d) utilize multiple media and technologies in order to communicate and know how to judge their effectiveness e) communicate effectively in diverse environments.
3. **Creativity:** By “creativity skill” we mean the ability to think creatively, which includes: a) constructing and generating new and useful ideas b) using a variety of techniques to create these ideas c) coming up with innovative, unique or imaginative solutions to problems d) implementing the creative ideas in tangible artefacts.
4. **Pedagogical methodologies:** ER4STEM has adopted constructionism as a foundational approach to designing workshops and robotic solutions and in the development of an integrated framework for inclusive learning and engagement with STEM. Key features of constructionism are its epistemology for learning portraying knowledge and meaning making as fallible [15] and its focus on learning while engaged in bricolage with digital artefacts [1].
5. **Mixed-gender teams:** Develop approaches to the orchestration of teamwork, with particular consideration of mixed-gender groups.
6. **Differentiation:** within student productions, teaching methods and the sequence and description of activities, prompt activity designers to consider differentiation, providing examples of how this can be achieved in relation to sample objectives.
7. **Multiple entry points:** highlight alternative entry points by including this aspect in the student learning process with examples; similarly include suggestions and examples within the first phase of the sequence and description of activities
8. **Evidence of learning:** evidence of learning: include examples of achievable and measurable objectives; provide examples of how student productions (artefacts of learning) and

reflections (as a form of student production) can demonstrate achievement in a range of objectives, including domain, technical and 21st Century skills.

9. **Changing attitudes towards STEM:** identify points for discussions about the work of scientists (including who scientists are), experiences of STEM subjects and robotics in relation to STE(A)M subjects and career

Curriculum Map – A Contextual Visualization on a Macro Level

The curriculum map is the contextual visualization of educational robotics learning opportunities, as organized content into a set of use cases and contexts, revolving around desired learning outcomes. It is a part of the context layer of the generic educational robotics curriculum under the ER4STEM project.

The inspiration behind the map are the city metro maps, visualizing possible ways to transfer from one point to another (prior knowledge, entry points and desired learning outcomes), the respective metro stations (the ER4STEM Activity Plans) that comprise metro lines (in our case – the learning paths, more about them in 3.2 of the current deliverable) and stations where lines could be changed.

Our work in this dimension focuses on what the central ideas are around which the activities evolve and how these are expressed in the robotic constructions. Powerful ideas are a central theoretical construct of constructionism and involve the use of knowledge in new ways where learners can establish personal epistemological connections with various domains of knowledge [3]. Furthermore, analyzing powerful ideas [4] describes them as domains of knowledge where many diverse topics or subjects co-exist and become explicit.

During the adaptation or the conceptual design of an educational robotics activity, the current contextual background of the ER4STEM might be applied as reference or as a guideline on choosing suitable activity, based on ER4STEM project partners' experience.

The rationale behind the generic educational robotics curriculum map, presented below, is multi-layered. On the one hand, as it organizes the Activity Plans developed by the project partners in a brief but yet structured way – e.g. by age group, targeted domains, etc., which enables it to serve as a table of contents for the Activity Plans. On the other hand, it will allow pedagogues, teachers and other relevant stakeholders, who are unfamiliar with the project's content, to construct an educational robotics curriculum on a higher level, based on their needs.

Figure 2 Draft Version of the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum Map

With this generic educational robotics frame, we want to assist teachers in adapting a learning path, consisting of a set of educational robotics activities, that are suitable for their students, based on specific objectives, prior knowledge requirements and the student's interests, strengths and even weaknesses, age and abilities. The idea we want to put forward with this generic educational robotics curriculum is that of an individual approach to every class or group of students. This resonates with the idea that the ER4STEM project aims to target all students – not only those who already have experience or are already passionate about robotics. We want to offer educational robotics as a tool for learning to every student, regardless of age, ability and prior knowledge.

3.2 GENERIC CURRICULUM: CONTENT

In this report, we present the current draft version of the Generic Curriculum content as it was in July 2018. This version will be updated and aligned with D4.3 Final Release of Activity Plans, which is in process of development) and it presented in D2.4 ER4STEM Curricula. It is important to note that D4.3 Final Release of Activity Plans and D2.4 ER4STEM Curricula are planned to be finalized in month 35 one month after this report, (D2.3) will be submitted.

Learning Paths - a Tool to Address Desired Learning Outcomes on a Meso Level

Specifically, to address the **meso level**, instead of following a top-down approach and looking at what should be learned in terms of educational robotics, we followed a bottom-up approach. Consequently, we analyzed how we can identify teaching and learning elements, which are connected to the nature of educational robotics: i.e. constructionist technology, multidisciplinary domain, subject matter (for instance STEAM and Business) and a domain for contextualized learning of other subject matters. To visualize that, we introduced the concept of **learning paths**.

A learning path, as understood under the ER4STEM project, is a tool introduced to address desired learning outcomes through a set of use cases. A learning path consists of a set of educational robotics workshops or single activities within the workshops Activity Plans, which are suitable for a given context, students, specific objectives and prior knowledge. The learning paths are of a generic nature, meaning that they are designed to be further adapted and modified by teachers, willing to implement a specific learning path within their own unique learning context.

The learning paths as a concept, are understood as a curriculum property of a suggestive nature. What this means is that the learning paths present certain relationships between the ER4STEM Activity Plans – the **Activity Plans are connected to each other where a common desired learning outcome is identified, or a common context, such as technology or applied programming languages are taught**. However, educators who might analyze some Activity Plans are bound to find other relationships between Activity Plans, other learning outcomes that might suit their classroom needs, as well as identify other learning paths that might better fit their context. Thus, the learning paths identified by ER4STEM, are the learning paths identified in correspondence to the ER4STEM values and/or are the most commonly addressed in discussions with relevant stakeholders. The learning paths are meant to be taken as an opportunity, suggestion and guidelines for the educators, not as a strict sequence of Activity Plans that has to be followed, or as a learning plan.

We realize that a lot of the teachers that might address the generic curriculum map, will want to apply educational robotics Activity Plans with students with no prior experience or no established motivation

in robotics whatsoever. By the same token, among ER4STEM’s core values is to address all children. This is why this generic educational robotics curriculum applies and maintains the concept of **entry points**. Those entry points are represented as **dashed ovals** in the current version of the generic curriculum map.

As a general entry point, we consider educational robotics activities that do not require any prior knowledge. This allows a student with no prior experience in the field to enter at multiple levels, working with different technologies, and targeting a variety of domains. After completing an entry point activity, a student might continue, based on their interest, their journey in robotics following different activities, based on their interests and/or specific objectives. Activities, which we consider as entry points will be specially marked as such within the generic curriculum map that will be presented in D2.4. The current version of the generic curriculum map will only focus on showcasing the relationship between the ER4STEM activities, carried out in year 3 and demonstrate a draft version of the generic curriculum map, that will be further improved in D2.4.

The generic curriculum map and the learning paths, identified within this deliverable, will be further enriched with Activity Plans, designed within year 3 of the ER4STEM implementation period, to possibly form a new learning path by themselves or enrich other learning paths. Deliverable 2.4 will present the final version of the generic curriculum map with its learning paths, with a better graphical representation and structured visualization. Deliverable 2.4 will also present the end product, which educators and end beneficiaries of the curriculum will see, and apply.

With this generic educational robotics curriculum, we want to assist teachers in adapting a learning path, consisting of a set of educational robotics workshops or single activities within the workshop Activity Plans, that are suitable for their context, students, specific objectives and prior knowledge. The six educational paths built around the STEM domains, are based on the following use cases:

1. Technology and Engineering with LEGO

Technology and Engineering with LEGO															
Brief description of the use case: An educator aims to teach technology and engineering with LEGO robots . This is a typical use case of using robots for education.															
Suitable for: in-school and for extra-curricular Total duration: 47.5 h Robots: LEGO Robots; Programming Languages: LEGO Programming	<table border="1"> <caption>STEM Domain Distribution</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>STEM Domain</th> <th>Value</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Science</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Technology</td> <td>8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Engineering</td> <td>8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Mathematics</td> <td>6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Business</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Arts</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	STEM Domain	Value	Science	0	Technology	8	Engineering	8	Mathematics	6	Business	0	Arts	2
STEM Domain	Value														
Science	0														
Technology	8														
Engineering	8														
Mathematics	6														
Business	0														
Arts	2														
Social & action: Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice, analysis and synthesis of solutions. Taking and exchanging roles in a group. Communicate with other groups to find solutions Argumentation and fostering of maker culture: Class discussion; Students make and test hypotheses in practice about the robot actions based on their own program, make assumptions, test possible solutions, trying to develop their strategy in order to achieve the best solution, choose the															

best solution, communicate with other “makers”, collaborate with others “makers”, decision taking, brainstorming, identifying an authentic problem, make assumptions.

STEM Concept: **S:** direction, speed; **T:** code, using sequential programming, loops, selection; sequential programming; **E:** robot, servo motors, circuits, sensors; **M:** angle, curve, square, right angle, multiplication, proportions

2. Science, Technology and Engineering (multiple technologies)

Science, Technology and Engineering (multiple technologies)															
<p>Brief description of the use case: An educator aims to teach concepts of science, technology and engineering while demonstrating various technology platforms such as Arduino, BeeBots, Hedgehog, LEGO Mindstorms and LEGO WeDo as well as a vast plethora of programming languages C++, Python, LEGO Mindstorms Programming, Scratch or SNAP.</p>															
<p>Suitable for: in-school activity Total duration: 77.5 h Robots: Arduino, Hedgehog, LEGO Mindstorms, LEGO WeDo Programming Languages: Arduino IDE (C++), Python, LEGO Mindstorms Programming, Scratch/SNAP</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>Bar Chart Data</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Subject</th> <th>Score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Science</td> <td>8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Technology</td> <td>8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Engineering</td> <td>9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Mathematics</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Business</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Arts</td> <td>3</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Subject	Score	Science	8	Technology	8	Engineering	9	Mathematics	5	Business	2	Arts	3
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Business	2														
Arts	3														
<p>Social & action: Creativity, learn and practice how to construct and generate innovative ideas; Develop collaborative skills, fostering of presentation skills, take roles within groups, solve practical problems as a team, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, compare strategies and artefacts.</p> <p>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture: Communication: While working in teams, students build a robot following generic guidelines. They have to clearly communicate their plans and ideas how to construct the body of the robot to correctly connect the electronics and to program the robot. Students are made aware by tutors that they would make mistakes and have to identify and rework the corresponding parts in order to build and program the robot. ; Practice making conjectures about how the robot will react based on the program given. ; Students make and test hypotheses in practice about the robot actions based on their own program, make assumptions, test possible solutions, trying to develop their strategy in order to achieve the best solution; Identifying an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution.</p> <p>STEM Concept: S: distance, direction, speed, orientation; T: code, using sequential programming, loops, selection; E: robot, robotics elements, Arduino microcontrollers, motor drivers, ultrasonic sensors, servo motors, circuits, analog and digital sensor; M: angle, curve, square, right angle, multiplication, rectangle, proportions, dimensions, variables, geometry patterns</p>															

3. Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM)

Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM)															
<p>Brief description of the use case: An educator aims to cover all STEM domains, Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics, while also developing creativity among the students.</p>															
<p>Suitable for: in-school activity Total duration: 56 h Robots: Arduino, Finch, LEGO WeDo, Thymio; CBiS RobotArm Kit Programming Languages: Aseba, Scratch/SNAP, Blockly</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>Bar Chart Data</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Domain</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Science</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Technology</td> <td>7</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Engineering</td> <td>8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Mathematics</td> <td>6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Business</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Arts</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Domain	Count	Science	5	Technology	7	Engineering	8	Mathematics	6	Business	0	Arts	2
Domain	Count														
Science	5														
Technology	7														
Engineering	8														
Mathematics	6														
Business	0														
Arts	2														
<p>Social & action: Creativity, learn and practice how to construct and generate innovative ideas; Develop problem solving skills; Exercise effective communication skills; Encourage flexibility and adaptability; Foster collaboration skills; Argumentation; School classes are split up into groups. Each group has its own area of responsibility (design, programming etc.); Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, solve practical problems as a team, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips.</p> <p>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture: Communication: While working in teams, students build a robot following generic guidelines. They have to clearly communicate their plans and ideas. Students would make mistakes and have to identify and rework the corresponding parts in order to build and program the robot; Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas; Encourage curiosity; Encourage tinkering and experimentation; decision-making process within a team; Identifying and solving problems; Stimulate proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programming, as well as on a physical level with the robot. Exercise logical thinking; Practice making conjectures about how the robot will react based on the program given.</p> <p>STEM Concept: S: direction, distance, speed, orientation; T: code, using sequential programming, loops, selection; sequential programming; E: robot, servo motors, circuits, sensors robot, robotics elements, Arduino microcontrollers, motor drivers, ultrasonic sensors; horizontal sensors, ground sensors; event-based programming; M: two and three dimensional coordinate systems, proportion, symmetry, angles, types of triangles by length of sides (scalene, isosceles, equilateral), types of triangles by width of angles (acute, right, obtuse), circles, radius, diameter, functions (multiplication addition, subtraction and division), positive and negative numbers, whole numbers and decimal numbers, dimensions, variables.</p>															

4. "White-Box" Science, Technology and Engineering

"White-Box" Science, Technology and Engineering															
<p>Brief description of the use case: An educator aims to teach concepts in science, technology and engineering through "white box" platforms such as: Arduino, Hedgehog, LEGO WeDo with a stronger focus on electronics and widely used industrial programming languages such as C++ and Python</p>															
<p>Suitable for: in-school activity Total duration: 42 h Robots: "All White Box:" Arduino, Hedgehog, LEGO WeDo; Programming Languages: Arduino IDE (C++), Python, Scratch</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>Bar Chart Data</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Subject</th> <th>Score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Science</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Technology</td> <td>7</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Engineering</td> <td>8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Mathematics</td> <td>6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Business</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Arts</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Subject	Score	Science	5	Technology	7	Engineering	8	Mathematics	6	Business	5	Arts	2
Subject	Score														
Science	5														
Technology	7														
Engineering	8														
Mathematics	6														
Business	5														
Arts	2														
<p>Social & action: Creativity, learn and practice how to construct and generate innovative ideas; Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, solve practical problems as a team, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips.</p> <p>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture: Communication: While working in teams, students build a robot following generic guidelines. They have to communicate clearly their plans and ideas. Students would make mistakes and have to identify and rework the corresponding parts in order to build and program the robot; Class discussions; Practice making conjectures about how the robot will react based on the program given; Identifying an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution.</p> <p>STEM Concept: S: direction, speed, distance; T: loops; E: robot, robotics elements, Arduino microcontrollers, motor drivers, ultrasonic sensors, servo motors, circuits, analogue and digital sensors, distance sensors, servo motors, circuits, resistance, led, sensors (piezo, sonar); M: angle, curve, right angle, rectangle, dimensions, variables, geometry patterns</p>															

5. Technology, Mathematics and Arts

Technology, Mathematics and Arts	
<p>Brief description of the use case: An educator aims to teach Mathematics by using educational robotics technology. This path covers multiple mathematical concepts and applies art and real-life problems for self-expression and teaching advanced technological principles related to programming and mathematical concepts;</p>	

<p>Suitable for: in-school activity Total duration: 47.4 h Robots: Dash and Dot; Finch (can be replaced by Dash and Dot), SLurtles (virtual robot), CBiS RobotArm Kit Programming Languages: Drag and Drop, Scratch</p>	<table border="1"> <caption>Subject Distribution Data</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Subject</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Science</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Technology</td> <td>8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Engineering</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Mathematics</td> <td>6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Business</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Arts</td> <td>3</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Subject	Count	Science	0	Technology	8	Engineering	0	Mathematics	6	Business	0	Arts	3
Subject	Count														
Science	0														
Technology	8														
Engineering	0														
Mathematics	6														
Business	0														
Arts	3														
<p>Social & action: Develop collaborative skills, learn how to take turns and listen to each other, reach a compromise and decision etc.; Allowed students to collaborate and share ideas with each other, and, to learn that decision making processes are enhanced when being teams/groups. Develop an awareness of how to communicate with others in a virtual world. Develop written communication skills. Communicating with others. Develop written communication skills. Develop an awareness of how to communicate with others in a virtual world. Working with others in small groups to solve a problem. Presenting incomplete solutions to others. Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas. Encourage curiosity; Encourage tinkering and experimentation; The games require the decision-making process within a team; □ Identifying and solving problems; □ Stimulate proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programing, as well as on a physical level with the robot. Exercise logical thinking;</p> <p>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture: Groups were encouraged to make the robot intelligent and to work at any point in time and not only once. They were encouraged to test before they tell the tutors that their work was ready. Finding multiple solutions to activities, allowing the robot to respond to external stimuli/obstacles. Application of mathematical knowledge to solve problems. Awareness that there are multiple ways to solve a given problem. Reflection for learning. Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas. Encourage curiosity; Encourage tinkering and experimentation; □ The games require the decision-making process within a team; Identifying and solving problems; Stimulate proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programing, as well as on a physical level with the robot. Exercise logical thinking;</p> <p>STEM Concept: T: loops, If-then, If-else, repeat-until E: robot, sensors M: two and three dimensional coordinate systems, proportion, symmetry, square, angle (as a turn); probability, random numbers, variables; triangle, properties of shapes, cube, parallelogram, properties of 2D and 3D shapes, symmetry, square and its properties, properties of 2D shapes, triangles, types of triangles and properties, polygons, irregular shapes, 3D shapes, angles, acute and obtuse angles, angles, types of triangles by length of sides (scalene, isosceles, equilateral), types of triangles by width of angles (acute, right, obtuse), circles, radius, diameter, functions (multiplication addition, subtraction and division), positive and negative numbers, whole numbers and decimal numbers, variables</p>															

6. Technology, Engineering and Mathematics

<p>Suitable for: in-school activity Total duration: 46.9h Robots: Finch (can be replaced by LEGO Mindstorms), SLurtles (virtual robot), LEGO Mindstorms Programming Languages: Scratch, LEGO Mindstorms</p>	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Subject</th> <th>Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Science</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Technology</td> <td>9</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Engineering</td> <td>7</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Mathematics</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Business</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Arts</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Subject	Count	Science	5	Technology	9	Engineering	7	Mathematics	4	Business	0	Arts	2
Subject	Count														
Science	5														
Technology	9														
Engineering	7														
Mathematics	4														
Business	0														
Arts	2														
<p>Social & action: Develop an awareness of how to communicate with others in a virtual world. Develop written communication skills. Communicating with others. Develop written communication skills. Develop an awareness of how to communicate with others in a virtual world. Working with others in small groups to solve a problem. Presenting incomplete solutions to others. Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas. Encourage curiosity; Encourage tinkering and experimentation; The games require the decision-making process within a team; □ Identifying and solving problems; Stimulate proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programing, as well as on a physical level with the robot. Exercise logical thinking; Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, compare strategies and artefacts; taking and exchanging roles in a group. Communicate with other groups to find solutions</p> <p>Argumentation and fostering of maker culture: Application of mathematical knowledge to solve problems. Awareness that there are multiple ways to solve a given problem. Reflection for learning. Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas. Encourage curiosity; Encourage tinkering and experimentation; □ The games require the decision-making process within a team; Identifying and solving problems; Stimulate proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programing, as well as on a physical level with the robot. Exercise logical thinking; Students make and test hypotheses in practice about the robot actions based on their own program, make assumptions, test possible solutions, trying to develop their strategy in order to achieve the best solution. Identifying an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions choose the best solution, communicate with other “makers”.</p> <p>STEM Concept: T: loops, sequential programming ; E: sensors, ultrasonic sensor, light sensor, motors M: square, angle (as a turn); probability, random numbers, variables; triangle, properties of shapes, cube, parallelogram, properties of 2D and 3D shapes, symmetry, square and its properties, properties of 2D shapes, triangles, types of triangles and properties, polygons, irregular shapes, 3D shapes, angles, acute and obtuse angles, angles, types of triangles by length of sides (scalene, isosceles, equilateral), types of triangles by width of angles (acute, right, obtuse), circles, radius, diameter, functions (multiplication addition, subtraction and division), positive and negative numbers, whole numbers and decimal numbers, variables</p>															

Activity Plans – The Building Blocks of the ER4STEM Curriculum Paths

Within the generic curriculum map, presented as Figure 2 of the current deliverable, and in order to construct the learning paths, presented above, we applied the activity plans, applied in year 3 of the ER4STEM project implementation. Within the tables below (Table 1 and Table 2), we will give more details on the activity plans analyzed and used to create the current version of the curriculum map. In

Table 1, we will provide a legend to translate the activity plan codes, implemented within the generic curriculum map. Table 1 will be an integrated part of the generic curriculum map within D2.4 and will serve as part of the map's "legend". Through this table, the relevant stakeholders will be able to identify all activity plans included in a current path and further analyses them.

In Table 2, we present an analysis of the activity plans for year 3 provided by the project partners until July 2018. We have used this table in order to analyse and display the relationships between activity plans and to structure the activity paths, which we presented above. This table is not part of the generic curriculum or the curriculum map itself, but it is a part of the analysis of the activity plans, included within the map, and through it, we could explain the common criteria, through which we grouped certain activity plans to create a learning path.

Both tables will be further updated in D2.4, so that we could confirm with all partners details around their activity plans and improve the analysis of the activity plans. We could possibly enrich further Table 2 with more criteria for analysing the activity plans.

Table 1 A reference table of activity plans codes and activity plans names as applied in the current version of the generic educational robotics curriculum

CODE	ACTIVITY PLAN NAME	PARTNER ACRONYM
AL01	Exploring with Dash and Programming with Dash	AcrossLimits
AL02	Engaging with Robots in a Fun Way	AcrossLimits
CU01	Basic Introduction to SLurtles	Cardiff University
CU02	SLurtles Introduction, Orientation and Constructing	Cardiff University
CU03	Building Our Virtual World	Cardiff University
ES01	Educational Robotics and Creativity Workshop	ESI CEE
ES02	Visualizing Mathematics with the MathBot	ESI CEE
ES03	Educational Robotics for Sustainability and Life Skills	ESI CEE
PR01	Design Thinking and Robotics Workshop	PRIA
PR02	Elementary LEGO Mindstorms	PRIA
PR03	Robotics 4 Kids	PRIA
TW01	Basic introduction into robotics and VPL	TUWien
TW02	Robot Elevator	TUWien
UA01	Exploring Planet Ektonis	UoA
UA02	Insects' Battle	UoA
UA03	Park the Robot	UoA
UA04	Robot Olympics	UoA
UA05	Robotic Insect	UoA
UA06	Building Container Houses with a CNC Drawing Machine	UoA
UA07	Building a Robot and Making it Smart	UoA

Table 2 ER4STEM Activity Plans Analysis for Representation as Generic Curricula Elements

Code	Suitable for ER4STEM Age Group			Prior knowledge	Knowledge	Out of school	Robot	Program ming language	Duration in hours	Science	Technology	Engineering	Mathematics	Business	Arts	Technology use	Social & action	Argumentation and fostering of maker culture
	7 - 10	11 - 14	15 - 18															
AL01		y		No ->			Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals	8		10		10			Using remote control and Drag and Drop visuals	Develop collaborative skills, learn how to take turns and listen to each other, reach a compromise and decision etc.	Groups were encouraged to make the robot intelligent and to work at any point in time and not only once.
AL02	y			Yes	Knowledge of Scratch language for a few of the students which helped with programming of Dash; very few others had attended LEGO Mindstorms classes. Other students had no previous knowledge in programming or robotics.		Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals	8		10		10			Drag and drop visuals	Develop collaborative skills, learn how to take turns and listen to each other, reach a compromise and decision etc.	Groups were encouraged to make the robot intelligent and to work at any point in time and not only once.

CU01	y			No ->		Slurtles	Scratch for OpenSim	3		10		3			Programming interface - Scratch for OpenSim; Virtual world – SLurtle World (internal access only); Robot – Slurtles (cuboids)	Develop an awareness of how to communicate with others in a virtual world. Developed to foster collaboration.	Application of mathematical knowledge to solve problems. Awareness that there are multiple ways to solve a given problem. Reflection for learning. Developed to foster thinking and problem-solving skills.
CU02		y		No ->		Slurtles	Scratch for OpenSim	8.2		10		3			Programming interface - Scratch for OpenSim; Virtual world – SLurtle World (internal access only); Robot – Slurtles (cuboids)	Develop an awareness of how to communicate with others in a virtual world. Developed to foster collaboration and creativity.	Application of mathematical knowledge to solve problems. Awareness that there are multiple ways to solve a given problem. Reflection for learning. Developed to foster collaboration, creativity, critical thinking, and teamwork and problem-solving skills.

CU03	y		Yes	Experience in virtual worlds, programming SLurples to build 2D shapes, communicating with others in the virtual world, documenting their work using screenshots and Sways.		Slurples	Scratch for OpenSim	8.2		10		3		3	Practice and develop programming skills with a graphical environment (Scratch for OpenSim). Develop 3D spatial awareness.	Develop an awareness of how to communicate effectively with others in a virtual world. Developed to foster collaboration and creativity.	Design and create an interactive object within the virtual world. Application of mathematical knowledge to solve problems. Awareness that there are multiple ways to solve a given problem. Explain ideas to others. Identify and solve problems together. Reflection for learning.
ES01	y	y		No ->	Suitable for an extra-curricular activity	Arduino	Scratch	8	5	10	10				Arduino custom robotics kit.	Creativity: within the workshop students learn and practice how to construct and generate innovative ideas to address real life problems using Tony Buzan mind-mapping techniques. Collaboration:	Communication: While working in teams, students build a robot following generic guidelines. They have to clearly communicate their plans and ideas how to construct the body of the

																	While students in each team are changing their roles during each task, they learn how to work effectively and respectfully with others in order and to build relevantly complex robotics system.	robot to correctly connect the electronics and to program the robot.
ES02	y	y	Yes	Assumed third grade (Bulgarian education system) mathematics knowledge. Basic command of Scratch is a recommendation but not an obligation.		The Finch robot	Scratch	8	5	10			Programming The Finch robot developed by Birdbrain Technologies with the visual programming software Scratch.	Develop problem solving skills; · Exercise effective communication skills; · Encourage flexibility and adaptability; · Foster collaboration skills; Argumentation	Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas. · Encourage curiosity; · Encourage tinkering and experimentation;			

ES03	y	y		No ->	Suitable for an extra-curricular activity	The RobotArm kit by CBiS Education	Scratch	4	3	4			Programming the RobotArm kit by CBiS Education through the visual programming software Scratch.	Develop problem solving skills; Exercise effective communication skills; Encourage flexibility and adaptability; Foster collaboration skills;	Practicing communication skills in terms of formulating and expressing ideas. Encourage curiosity; Encourage tinkering and experimentation; The games require the decision-making process within a team; Identifying and solving problems; Stimulate proportional thinking and proportional reasoning by thinking in proportion to solve the mathematical tasks while visualizing the solution both on the screen by programming, as well as on a physical level with the robot.
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																			Exercise logical thinking;
PR01	y	y		Yes	Basic reading skills and understanding of numeric values; Basic knowledge of working with computers is advantageous.		Hedgehog	Python	8		6	10					Hedgehog Educational Robotics Controller	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice, fostering of presentation and argumentation skills. Skills to be fostered are collaboration, teamwork, critical thinking.	Practice explanation and justification of ideas, make assumptions, test possible solutions, and choose the best solution. Designed to foster collaboration, teamwork and critical thinking skills.

PR02	y			Yes	Little if any knowledge of the LEGO Mindstorms EV3 kit; Reading and writing skills		LEGO Mindstorms	Drag and Drop Visuals	8		6	10					LEGO EV3 programming environment	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice, fostering of presentation and argumentation skills. Skills to be fostered are collaboration, teamwork, critical thinking.	Practice explanation and justification of ideas, make assumptions, test possible solutions, and choose the best solution. Designed to foster collaboration, teamwork and critical thinking skills.
PR03	y	y		Yes	Little if any knowledge of the LEGO Mindstorms EV3 kit; reading and writing skills; basic knowledge of working with computers is advantageous		LEGO EV3	Drag and Drop Visuals	18 hours		6	10					LEGO EV3 programming environment	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice, fostering of presentation and argumentation skills. Skills to be fostered are collaboration, creativity,	Practice explanation and justification of ideas, make assumptions, test possible solutions, and choose the best solution. Designed to foster collaboration, teamwork and critical thinking skills.

UA02			y	Yes	Little if any knowledge of Arduino. Students are experts in electronics and/or have mastery in computer science & programming concepts.	Suitable for an extra-curricular activity	Arduino	Arduino IDE	12	5	8	8				Programming with Arduino. Skills to be fostered are collaboration, teamwork, problem solving and leadership.	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, and communicate with other groups to exchange ideas, tips and advices. Skills to be fostered are collaboration, teamwork, problem solving, and leadership.	Make assumptions, test possible solutions and choose the best solution. Skills to be fostered are collaboration, creativity, teamwork, critical thinking, and problem solving.
UA03			y	y	No ->	Suitable for an extra-curricular activity	LEGO NXT	LEGO EV3	8		10	5	7			Programming with LEGO NXT in LEGO programming environment	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, compare strategies and artefacts	Students make and test hypotheses in practice about the robot actions based on their own program, make assumptions, test possible solutions, trying to develop their strategy in order to achieve the best solution.

UA04	y	y		Yes	Little knowledge in Robotics; Basic knowledge in programming;	Suitable for an extra-curricular activity	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO EV3	6	7	9	8	9			Programming LEGO in LEGO programming environment	Develop collaborative skills; communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips.	The aim of the work is to understand the importance of sensors in the control of robotic structures, as well as the natural laws behind human activity.
UA05		y	y	Yes	Little knowledge of Arduino and electronic parts (resistances, led). Before this project students were involved in activities in order to get familiar with electronic circuits and Arduino board; Good knowledge of programming concepts (like if-then concepts);	Suitable for an extra-curricular activity	Arduino	Arduino IDE	6	8	8	8		4	Design with Arduino Uno board, a mini breadboard, some electronic parts (resistances, led, sonar sensor, piezo, servomotor) and programming with open-source Arduino Software (IDE). Skills to be fostered are collaboration, creativity, teamwork, critical thinking and problem solving.	Improve collaborative skills, exchange ideas, and take roles within groups. Skills to be fostered are collaboration, teamwork and leadership.	Identifying an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions, choose the best solution. Skills to be fostered are collaboration, creativity, teamwork, leadership.	

UA06	y	No ->	Suitable for an extra-curricular activity	LEGO Mindstorms	Logo and LEGO	6	10	7	10	Programming with Logo and LEGO NXT MINDSTORMS programming environment	Develop collaborative skills, take roles within groups, communicate with other groups to exchange ideas and tips, advice, analysis and synthesis of solutions	Argue about what a camp needs, therefore what solids they need to create and for what reasons. Argue about the spatial arrangement of the camp so that it will be able to support the needs of the people who live there. Practice making conjectures about how the real machine moves in order to cut steel nets which when tiled create container houses. Practice making conjectures about how the robot will move in order to draw nets which when tiled create houses models. Make
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																		assumptions, test possible solutions choose the best solution, communicate with other "makers".
UA07	y	y		No ->	Suitable for an extra-curricular activity	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms	7.5		10	6	2		2	Programming in LEGO programming environment, assembling LEGO sensors and motors	Taking and exchanging roles in a group. Communicate with other groups to find solutions	Identifying an authentic problem, make assumptions, test possible solutions choose the best solution, communicate with other "makers".	

3.3 GENERIC CURRICULUM: PROCESS OF THE ERW IMPLEMENTATION AND DELIVERY

While the PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITIES PROCESS described in D 1.2 FRAMEWORK (Chapter 5, pp 24 -25) informs on the process of the ERW implementation and Delivery, the scope of the process of the ERW implementation is limited to the adaptation and delivery of the workshops and does not cover educational robotics workshops pedagogical design, which is a subject of WP4.

Description and support of the educational robotics workshops implementation process aims to provide a clear picture to researchers and teachers on the key steps that were planned and executed within the second year of the project implementation. From a research perspective, the process complements the evaluation data received from the workshops with detailed information on how this data was generated through the educational robotics workshops execution. This section of the report represents the process as it was implemented within the second year of the project.

The process description is continuously updated based on the experience gained and serves as a reference during the remaining implementation phases of the project and therefore, for any stakeholders that might be interested in the application of the Activity Plans and similarly, to deliver the ERWs designed and elaborated on within the ER4STEM project.

The educational robotics workshops delivery process contains four phases, namely Initiation, Preparation, Execution, and Closure that are visually represented within the process scheme as horizontal lines. Those phases follow the basic content structure on a macro level of the ER4STEM project framework, and namely level two – implementation and level four – improvement (where the process gives evaluation guidelines, crucial for the improvement of the workshop, regardless of research purposes). The “Prepare ERW delivery” and “Deliver ERW” steps are presented in more details as sub-processes. Each process step contains overall the following properties:

- *Entry criteria*: criteria, which determines when the respective step can be started.
- *Inputs*: materials, results from other steps and other items that are needed for the proper execution of the corresponding steps.
- *Outputs*: results produced during the corresponding steps.
- *Exit criteria*: criteria, which determines whether the respective step could be considered, completed.

The process description included in this report incorporates changes and improvements made throughout Y2 and serves as an updated version of the process already published in D2.1 in Y2. Although the updates do not change the process’s structure, they reflect on two very important issues 1) the need for closer cooperation with teachers/tutors for the workshops and educational materials’ organization and preparation and 2) alignment of the workshops content to the curricula of other disciplines, included but not limited to since, technology, engineering and mathematics domains.

Other important changes were associated with the related artefacts and methods. More specifically the changes were:

- In Y2, a new improved version of the Workshops Activity Plans was used. This version of the activity plans provided more explicit links to the targeted skills and recommendations and how they can be addressed by the incorporated activity blocks. The activity plans used in Y2

will be described in details in D4.2 Operational Release of Activity Plans. The generic educational robotics curriculum framework, presented in this deliverable is built upon and follows the activity plans' structure from year 2.

- In Y2, improvements in the evaluation method and tools were introduced. Those improvements are described in further detail in D6.4 Evaluation and Analysis of 2nd Project Year.

ERW Implementation Process Description

The ERW Implementation process, presented in **Error! Reference source not found.** starts with an Initiation phase. At this stage, the major objective is to identify, through the aid of the curriculum map, desired learning outcomes, that might overlap with those covered by ER4STEM, as well as assess if the curriculum map covers the available technology of the educator, or the programming languages taught already. Identifying those will make it easier to identify possible support provided by the educational robotics framework in order to make all relevant stakeholders aware and to establish the generic learning objectives on a contextual level. Once the stakeholders are committed to the ERW, we enter into the Preparation phase in which an individual curriculum is tailored from the ER4STEM generic curricula and the content of the curriculum is documented in Activity plan aligned to the stated learning objectives. Commitment from all ERW stakeholders is obtained and the ERW is prepared in terms of space, team, materials and evaluation (see Figure 4 Prepare for ERW Delivery Sub-process).

Within the next phase, an ERW is delivered, while the team is performing continuous evaluation (see Figure 4 Deliver ERW Sub-process). The process ends with an analysis and this way, the evaluation results enter the next cycle in order to improve the future educational robotics workshops.

Figure 3 ERW Implementation Process (updated version)

PROCESS ELEMENTS

INITIATION PHASE

SELECT GENERIC CURRICULUM PATH (NEW STEP)

Description

An educator or a representative of the Implementation Team conducts an initial analysis of the generic educational robotics curriculum, to identify possible learning paths or single activities that might be useful to their specific context.

- Analyse the experience already shared within the ER4STEM Repository at repository.er4stem.com.
- Assess and select among activities or learning paths within the curriculum map, which might support the specific learning objectives and context.
- Possibly, obtain Activity Plans, Activity Reports and, potentially, evaluation data for workshops, conducted under the Activity Plans of interest.
- Other;

Entry criteria

Desire to implement educational robotics workshops, to support specific learning goals.

Inputs

- Generic Curriculum Map – information on both the context and the content, the process of the generic curriculum on educational robotics, as well as awareness of the support that it might provide to attain specific learning objectives. (Summarized information will be available within the ER4STEM Repository at repository.er4stem.com and in detail in the D2.4 ER4STEM Curricula and in the D1.4 ER4STEM: An Operational and Conceptual Framework for Educational Robotics);
- Activity Plans including key information how to organize the workshop. Summarized information will be available within ER4STEM Repository at repository.er4stem.com;
- References from teachers or workshop leaders, including custom materials, video, “how – to” and others. Summarized information will be available within ER4STEM Repository at repository.er4stem.com;

Outputs

- A list of relevant activities and learning paths, which might provide support to the design and implementation of educational robotics activities.
- Analysis on how the educational robotics workshops correspond to the curricula related to other disciplines related to science, technology, engineering and mathematics.
- Awareness on the general implementation criteria, target groups, learning objectives.
- Analysis and assessment of the available infrastructure, which might be of use for the implementation of educational robotics workshop.

Exit criteria

Learning paths and Activity Plans are looked into and one or more of them are selected as a baseline for the design and implementation of educational robotics workshops.

 AWARE STAKEHOLDERS**Description**

A representative/representatives of the Implementation Team takes actions for raising awareness within the target groups about the benefits of integrating ER in the educational process. One or several awareness activities could be performed within this step:

- Distribution of awareness materials via electronic channels such as e-mail, social media, broadcasting.
- Consultations with teachers on specific subjects related to science, technology, engineering and mathematics, how their disciplines can be supported through educational robotics.
- Close cooperation with teachers and educators, if possible, in order to tailor the educational content presented in the workshop, to the student's needs. This means putting stronger focus on some concepts included already in the Activity Plans or the formulation of an entirely new Activity Plans and educational content.
- Participation in different educational events, such as workshops, conferences, meetings and others.
- Direct meetings with relevant stakeholders.
- Others.

Entry criteria

The educational robotics workshop is designed and prepared

Inputs

- Information and demonstration materials - video, printed materials, multimedia presentations, robots or robotic kits ready for demonstration, analysed data from previously implemented educational robotics workshops.
- Curricula of the targeted disciplines related to science, technology, engineering and mathematics.
- References from teachers, including material already covered throughout the school year in the official school curricula.
- Representatives from implementation team to be involved in this process are selected and the relevant materials are provided. Target groups are identified, as well as relevant educational events.

Outputs

- A list of relevant stakeholders, who are interested in participating in ERWs.
- Analysis how the educational robotics workshops correspond to the curricula related to other disciplines related to science, technology, engineering and mathematics.
- General requirements about the implementation of educational robotics workshops communicated to the interested parties.

Exit criteria

Stakeholders are interested in participating in and contributing to the educational robotics workshops.

ARE STAKEHOLDERS INTERESTED?

Gates

- NO
- YES

OBTAIN COMMITMENT FROM STAKEHOLDERS

Description

Representatives of the Implementation Team meet decision makers from the organization that will host/ organize the ERWs. Both parties discuss and agree on important aspects of the ERW delivery such as:

- ERW objectives and expected results related to the targeted discipline and curricula.
- Space and student's info.
- Technical requirements and necessary equipment.
- Content of written consent forms and evaluation procedure.

Entry criteria

The relevant stakeholder is interested to organize/contribute to an ERW, which is aligned with the general curricula of other disciplines related to science, technology, engineering and mathematics.

Inputs

- ERW Activity Plans;
- Written consent forms for parents, students and school;
- Information/ demonstration materials and presentations.

Outputs

- Alignment of the ERW Activity Plan to the specific objectives and curricula.
- Alignment of Written Consent Forms, if needed.
- Official agreement between implementation organization and hosting organization (if necessary).
- List of participants.
- Signed consent forms from parents, students and educational organization.

Exit criteria

Commitment to organize/contribute to the ERWs.

ARE STAKEHOLDERS COMMITTED?

Gates

YES, but alignment needed

YES

NO

PREPARATION PHASE

ALIGN LEARNING PATHS AND ACTIVITY PLANS

Description

The Implementation Team aligns, if possible and if necessary, the learning paths and the selected Activity Plans and/or Written Consent Forms to the needs and requirements of the stated objectives, curricula of other disciplines related to science, technology, engineering and mathematics or teachers' requirements. The needs and requirements may include:

- Specific educational objectives. For instance, objectives might need to be changed because students are already advanced in some of the topics covered by ERW or in case that the curricula on other disciplines require additional topics to be included in the workshop in order to meet educational objectives derived from other fields and subjects in science, technology, engineering and mathematics domains.
- Technical constraints derived from the environment. For example, the host organization does not have enough computers available or the computers might be running on a different operation system.
- Organizational requirements. For example, the host organization requires different social orchestration, such as number of students per class, specific criteria for setting up the teams or the available time slots are different from the originally planned time slots in the ERW Activity Plans.

The Implementation Team in cooperation with local teachers/tutors changes the original Workshop Activity Plan and/or Written Consent Forms, if possible, in order to satisfy the agreed on requirements provided by the hosting organization. Bi-directional traceability between the changed (aligned) Activity Plan/Written Consent Forms and related activities, materials and artefacts is ensured.

Entry criteria

Changes to the Activity Plan are requested and agreed on

Inputs

- Original ERW Activity Plan.
- Original Written Consent Forms.
- Information Materials.
- Alignment of requirements to the ERW Activity Plan.
- Alignment of requirements to the Written Consent Forms.

Outputs

- Aligned Activity Plan, including clear instruction how the implemented changes will affect the activities, materials and artefacts.
- Aligned written consent forms.

- Aligned information materials.

Exit criteria

Commitment to the Aligned Activity Plan and/or Written Consent Forms is obtained by all relevant stakeholders

OBTAIN COMMITMENT FROM ERW PARTICIPANTS

Description

The Implementation Team distributes information brochures and Written Consent Forms among the participants (students and their families), answers any questions, and comments that come from the participants or their parents.

Local teachers/tutors or scientists are committed to contribute to the ERWs and to learn how to implement them.

Majority of the participants in the ERW sign written consent forms and are familiar with the study and the purpose of data collection and have understanding on how their identity and their data will be protected.

Entry criteria

Obtained commitment to the Activity Plans from the ERW organizers/ host

Inputs

- List of participants;
- Written Consent Forms Templates - for organizer/ host, for the participants and their parents.
- Information materials for the workshop, the project and the study.

Outputs

- Signed Written Consent Forms - by hosting organization, by parents and students.
- Updated list of participants with marked preferences for video or audio recording, agreement to participate in EC open data initiative, disagreement to participate in the specific ERW process and any other information, relevant to the ERW implementation.

Exit criteria

All participants and relevant stakeholders provided signed written consent forms. Updated list of participants is developed.

PREPARE FOR ERW DELIVERY

[Go to details of the sub-process](#)

Description

The Implementation Team prepares the workshop delivery

Entry Criteria

Commitment from all relevant stakeholders is obtained and the Activity Plans is aligned as needed.

Inputs

- Aligned Activity Plan including clear instructions how the implemented changes will affect the activities, materials and artefacts.
- Updated list of participants with marked preferences for video or audio recording, agreement to participate in EC open data initiative, disagreement to participate in the specific ERW process and any other information, relevant to the ERW implementation.
- Evaluation templates.
- Evaluation method.

Outputs

- Materials and artefacts prepared.
- Space and ICT environment ensured.
- Implementation team trained.
- Evaluation materials printed.

Exit Criteria

Outputs are finalized and ready

EXECUTION PHASE

DELIVER ERW

[Go to details of the sub-process](#)

Description

The Implementation team, ideally in cooperation with local teachers/tutors or scientists executes the ERW following the specific Activity Plans and observation/ assessment method, taking into account a target group on which the observation will focus.

Entry Criteria

Workshop prepared

Inputs

- Activity Plans.
- Materials and artefacts.
- Space and ICT environment.
- Implementation team (tutors) trained.
- Observation/ Assessment methods and tools.
- Tools, equipment and spare parts.

Outputs

- Educational results.
- Collected and processed artefacts and observation/ assessment forms.
- Reflections on ERW and improvement suggestions from implementation team and contributing teachers/tutors or scientists.

Exit Criteria

ERW finalized

CLOSURE PHASE

EVALUATE RESULTS

Description

The implementation team or external expert evaluates achieved educational results according to the educational objectives in the Activity Plans and observation/ assessment methodology. Members of the Implementation Team document good practices and issues that were observed and any ideas for improvements that were generated by the relevant stakeholders. Information includes:

- Source (who identified the issue).
- Observation (description of the issue).
- Cause (what caused the issue, if it can be readily identified).
- Suggested improvement (how to solve the problem).

Entry criteria

Delivered workshop

Inputs

- Evaluation method.
- Collected and filed in evaluation documents and educational artefacts.
- Tutor reflections and observations in raw format.
- Improvement suggestions.

Outputs

- Evaluation forms and sheets are filled in by participants and are collected, organized, anonymized and scanned to be further stored in the workshop data base.
- Signed written consent forms are processed and organized into folders.
- Other relevant artefacts of learning, such as code, mind maps, midpoint reflections, etc., are collected.
- Tutor documents, such as tutor observations and tutor reflections are completed;
- Video or audio interviews with preferably the target group from the study, are conducted, transcribed and encrypted.
- Sensitive data, such as participant key, name labels, certificates, photos, videos, etc., is encrypted and stored on an external hard drive.
- Suggestions for improvement and reflections on the workshop are taken into consideration and filed.

Exit criteria

Evaluated results.

Prepare for ERW Delivery Sub-process

Figure 4 Prepare for ERW delivery sub-process

PROCESS ELEMENTS

SET UP SPACE AND ENVIRONMENT

Description

The Implementation team checks the hall/s where the ERW will take place and ensures that the facilities and equipment correspond to the requirements of the activity, as defined in the respective Activity Plans. When applicable, the Implementation team installs necessary software on the computers that will be used by the students and tests it to make sure that the software is properly set up.

Entry criteria

Commitment from all relevant stakeholders is obtained and the Activity Plans is aligned as needed.

Inputs

- Aligned Activity Plan including clear instructions how to further involve local teachers/tutors or scientists and how the implemented changes will affect the activities, materials and artefacts.

Outputs

- Space and ICT environment.
- Access to an appropriate workshop hall guaranteed.
- Workshop desks, power supplies and other special tools/equipment ensured.
- ICT equipment ensured and set up as needed.

Exit criteria

Space and ICT requirements fulfilled.

 TRAIN THE IMPLEMENTATION TEAM

Description

All members of the implementation team, local teachers/tutors and participating scientists are trained how to facilitate the ERW. If necessary, the team can decide to simulate the workshop and all activities in it. Any specifics of the particular workshop are discussed and actions are planned.

Entry criteria

Commitment from all relevant stakeholders obtained and the Activity Plans is aligned as needed.

Inputs

- Aligned Activity Plan and/or Curriculum Path, including clear instructions how the implemented changes will affect the activities, materials and artefacts.
- Updated list of participants with written for video recording, agreement to participate in open data pilot, disagreement to participate in the specific ERW and any other information relevant to the ERW implementation.
- Evaluation templates.
- Evaluation method and protocol.

Outputs

- Implementation team, local teachers/tutors and participating scientists trained on:
 - Scenario.
 - Space and students' information.
 - Social orchestration.
 - Student productions and artefacts of learning.
 - Sequence and description of activities.
 - Evaluation procedures, interviews, reflections, observations and sensitive data.

Exit criteria

Implementation team is capable to execute the workshop

 SET UP MATERIALS AND ARTIFACTS

Description

The implementation team prepare the materials and artefacts for the ERW taking into account any specific requirements for the particular workshop. The activities can include:

- Disassembly/assembly of components of the robotic kits.
- Testing each kit/robot to ensure that it functions properly.
- Modification of students and teachers' guides.
- Others.

Integrity (e.g. right versions) of the materials and artefacts ensured.

Entry criteria

Commitment from all relevant stakeholders obtained and the Activity Plans is aligned as needed.

Inputs

- Aligned Activity Plans including clear instructions how the implemented changes will affect the activities, materials and artefacts.

Outputs

- Materials and artefacts prepared:
 - Digital artefacts.
 - Robotic artefacts.
 - Student's workbook and manual.
 - Teacher's instruction book and manual.

Exit criteria

Materials and artefacts ready.

PREPARE EVALUATION

Description

The implementation team prints the evaluation forms and ensures equipment for conducting the evaluation during the ERW delivery.

Entry criteria

Commitment from all relevant stakeholders obtained and the Activity Plan is aligned as needed.

Inputs

- Evaluation templates.
- Evaluation method and protocol; Updated list of participants with marked preferences for video recording, agreement to participate in open data pilot, disagreement to participate in the specific ERW and any other information relevant to the ERW implementation.

Outputs

- Evaluation materials printed and/or digitally prepared:
 - Draw a scientist form.
 - Pre-questionnaire form.
 - Post-questionnaire form.
 - Observation notes template.
 - Reflection sheet form.
 - Activity Plan Template.
 - Post-Activity Report Template.
- Focus group for observation and interviews identified.
- Evaluation equipment ready:
 - Camera.

- Audio/ video recorder.

Exit criteria

Evaluation prepared.

Deliver ERW Sub-process

Figure 5 Deliver ERW sub-process

PROCESS ELEMENTS

INTRODUCE STUDENT TO THE ERW CONTEXT

Description

The researcher introduces the implementation team, explain the ERW objectives, describe the ERW agenda and provides safety instructions. Explain that video/audio recording equipment will be/is set up in the room and why.

Entry criteria

ERW has started

Inputs

- Aligned Activity Plans;
- If conducted in a school, informed consent given by the school to carry out the research.
- Informed consent to collect and store data given by parents.
- Informed consent to collect and store data given by students.
- Informed consent to collect and store data given by tutors.
- Signed consent forms stored safely.
- Each student has randomly allocated a student number.

Outputs

- Tutors introduce themselves, the project, the workshop and the study - students are aware of the workshop context and about the study, they will take part in.
- Students are introduced to the evaluation methods, which will be applied during the workshops.

- Students understand that they do not have to consent to take part in the evaluation and that this will not result in any negative consequence for them.
- Students know that they can withdraw from the study at any time, without giving any explanation and this will not result in any negative consequence for them
- Students receive and understand safety instructions for participating in the ERW.

Exit criteria

Introduction done

DRAW A SCIENTIST AND PRE-QUESTIONNAIRE

Description

The implementation team asks students to draw a scientist at work according their notions and to fill in the pre-questionnaire form.

- Draw a scientist at work must be done before the first experience.
- Pre-questionnaire (online or paper copy) collects background information on students and requires their student number.

Entry criteria

Introduction done and students are aware about the ERW objectives.

Inputs

- Draw a scientist sheet.
- Pre-questionnaire evaluation form.
- Drawing or writing tools.
- Participant numbers stickers or other way to mark participants' work.

Outputs

- Filled in draw a scientist and pre-questionnaire sheets.

Exit criteria

Implementation team collected students' sheets: draw a scientist and pre-questionnaire

LEAD THE WORKSHOPS SESSIONS

Description

Following the Activity Plan, the implementation team informs students about robotic behaviours, the role of creator-programmer in giving desired functionalities and characteristics to a robotic device. Students are introduced to available parts, sensors, motors. Students create/ assemble robot devices from available parts or consider functionalities/ characteristics of pre-assembled available robotic devices. Students experiment with different values and settings and observe the results during the workshop. Students create programs for controlling the robotic devices. If robotic devices are pre-assembled, the students focus on programming and debugging their own programs. Implementation

team leads the students in researching connections with other scientific domains - mathematics, engineering, biology, chemistry etc.

Entry criteria

Collected filled in draw a scientist and pre-questionnaire sheets

Inputs

- Activity plan.
- Scenarios.
- Tested and assembled/ disassembled robotic kits.
- Installed programs and applications on student computers.
- Provided guides and instructions.

Outputs

- Pictures and videos (if applicable) of the workshop, the artefacts of learning, etc.
- Assembled robot devices.
- Collect the code that each team produced.
- Observation.
- Mid-point reflections conducted in a format suitable to the case.
- Other artefacts - research description, project design description, problem description etc.

Exit criteria

Collected artefacts of students' work

CONTINUOUS OBSERVATION

Description

The implementation team follows assessment method and tools together with blank sheets of questionnaires and interview questions. The observation is implemented during the whole duration of the workshop. The observation can include one or more of the following elements:

- Interview with focus group(s) (implemented by implementation team).
- Peer assessment.
- Artefacts of learning (code, robots, plans, reflection, etc.).
- Observation notes (filled by the implementation team).
- Reflection sheet (filled by each member of implementation team).

Entry criteria

Designed and developed assessment method and tools.

Inputs

- Developed assessment method.
- Printed supporting documents for tutors (observation forms, interview questions, evaluation protocol, etc.).

- Signed written consent forms - by the host/ organizer of the workshop, parents, students;
- Awareness of the participants in the assessment/ observation, its goals, the evaluation protocol, data and identity protection policies.
- Implementation team is trained how to perform the observation-related activities.

Outputs

- Target group is observed and interesting moments, phrases, reactions are recorded; if audio or video equipment is used for recording, the equipment is also monitored, and observations are timestamped according to the recording.
- Tutor documents, such as tutor observations and tutor reflections are completed and stored in the workshop database.
- Observation is accompanied by evaluation forms and other evaluation-related documents and activities.
- If permitted, audio or video recordings are made.
- Conducted short "interviews" with groups, ask questions and if possible, record them to support the evaluation. Each team could write instead a short team reflection on what they have done so far in the format of a blog post. The team's response is discussed within the team (not a sub-set of the team) and is as honest as possible.

Exit criteria

Collected and filed all observation sheets and tools

CONCLUDE THE WORKSHOP

Description

The implementation team gives students feedback about the workshop, gives last minute advice, internet connections for more information and provides important conclusions. The implementation team collects all observation/ assessment sheets and announces the end of the workshop.

Entry criteria

Collected workshop artefacts and observation sheets.

Inputs

- Developed assessment method.
- Printed assessment tools and supporting documents for tutors (evaluation forms, draw a scientist sheets, interview questions, evaluation protocol sheets).
- Signed written consent forms - by the host/ organizer of the workshop, parents, students.
- Awareness of the participants in the assessment/ observation, its goals, the evaluation protocol, data and identity protection policies.
- Implementation team is trained how to perform the evaluation-related activities;
- Microphone and/or camera.
- Post-Questionnaire sheets printed out.

Outputs

- Evaluation forms and sheets are filled in by participants and are collected by tutors.
- Other relevant artefacts of learning, such as code, mind maps, midpoint reflections, etc., are collected.

- Tutor documents, such as tutor observations and tutor reflections are completed.
- Video or audio interviews with preferably the target group with minimum 2 students from the study are performed.

Exit criteria

Artefacts and observation sheets.

PERFORM FINAL EVALUATION

Description

The implementation team processes the collected and filed artefacts and observation sheets according to the evaluation protocol. According to the tutor experience and data (last if applicable), the implementation team suggests improvement actions. The Implementation team performs evaluation.

Entry criteria

Artefacts and evaluation sheets

Inputs

- Developed evaluation method.
- Printed assessment tools and supporting documents for tutors (evaluation forms, draw a scientist sheets, interview questions, evaluation protocol sheets).
- Signed written consent forms - by the host/ organizer of the workshop, parents, students.
- Awareness of the participants in the assessment/ observation, its goals, the evaluation protocol, data and identity protection policies.
- Implementation team is trained how to perform the evaluation-related activities;
- Camera and/or microphone.

Outputs

- Observations - video and audio recordings are used to finalise own observation notes.
- Sample materials that represent good practices
- Modified Activity Plans
- Others

Exit criteria

Processed data.

PERFORM FINAL EVALUATION

Description

The implementation team share its experience with other educators.

Entry criteria

Evaluation completed

Inputs

- Evaluation materials
- Registration in the ER4STEM Repository

Outputs

- Lessons learned
- Modified/improve Activity Plans
- New elements or whole ERW.

Exit criteria

Data uploaded in the ER4STEM repository.

4 ER4STEM WORKSHOPS PROGRESS REVIEW

Since the start of the ER4STEM project, for the period February 2016 – July 2018 in which WP2 was in implementation, a total of 190 educational robotics workshops with 4334 students or 107% of the planned students for the whole project were completed.

Within the period September 2017 to July 2018, the ER4STEM project partners organized 72 educational robotics workshops with 1676 participants, which is about 41% of the planned 4050 students for the whole project implementation phase.

March 2018 and May 2018 were the months, in which the highest student participation in the workshops was recorded. Detailed information about the workshops is presented in [Appendix 1 Quantitative data from the ERWs based on the Workshop Information Forms](#). The timeline of the ERWs implementation is illustrated in the [Figure 6](#) and [Figure 7](#).

Figure 6 Number of male and female students and number of workshops per month

Figure 7 Cumulative number of male and female students and number of workshops per month

A visual representation of the distribution of educational robotics workshops and the respective number of students per project partner can be seen in Figure 8. This distribution corresponds to the country in which the respective workshops were implemented. PRIA and TUWien implemented 22 workshops with 515 students in Austria and Italy (1 educational robotics workshop in Italy), ESI CEE implemented 15 workshops with 396 students in Bulgaria, UoA implemented 9 workshops with 145 students in Greece, AcrossLimits implemented 13 workshops with 269 students in Malta and Cardiff University implemented 13 educational robotics workshops with 351 students in UK.

Figure 8 Number of male and female students and number of ERW per project partner

The ERWs were highly appreciated by the students. On average, the workshops were rated by the students with 3.5 to 5 stars out of 5 possible (Figure).

Figure 8 Average number of stars given by ERWs participants per project partner

The participants in the workshops were well balanced in terms of gender (Figure 9). Female participants were 49% of the total number of students and male participants were 51% of the total number of students. With a few exceptions, there were no significant deviations between the shares of female

and male students based on variables such as implementing partner, robotics kit and programming languages, which yet makes the research rather balanced in terms of gender in the majority of its aspects.

Figure 9 Number of male and female participants

A total number of participants per workshop ranging between 20 and 29 students was applicable for 40 ERWs (56% of the total number of ERWs), which closely corresponds to the average number of students within a regular classroom in general education schools (Figure 10).

Figure 10 Distribution of number of ERWs by number of participants per ERW

Most of the ER4STEM project's students from the third year of the project implementation participated in ERW based on SLurtles (21%), followed by students that participated in workshops based on the Dash a Dot robotics kits (16%), Thymio II (14 %), Arduino robotics kits (12 %), and Hedgehog (11%). The remaining participants in the workshops used Finch (10%), and LEGO Mindstorms robotics kits (8%), Robotic Arm Kit - CBiS Education (3%), BotBall: Wallaby controller (3%), and LEGO WeDo (1%) (Figure 11). With the exception of the ERWs based on BotBall, the ERWs were generally gender balanced.

Robotic Arm Kit - CBiS Education robotic kit was introduced for first time during the third year of the project implementation and it proved to be successful in demonstrating the benefits of applying educational robotics as a medium to teach other disciplines such as mathematics.

Figure 11 Number of male and female students and number of ERW per robotics kit

The distribution of educational robotics based on the programming languages applied correlates with the distribution of the robotics kits that were used for the same ERWs (Figure 12). To demonstrate, 13 workshops that applied Dot and Dash robotics kits, used Drag and Drop Visuals as a programming language Likewise, the LEGO Mindstorms based workshops applied the LEGO Mindstorms programming environment, BotBall Link Controller based workshops applied the C programming language. The Thymio II based workshops incorporated ASEBRA. Scratch was an exception of this trend since it was used with Arduino, SLurtles, Finch, Robotic Arm Kit - CBiS Education and LEGO WeDo robotics kits.

Figure 12 Number of male and female students and number of ERW per programming language

One can notice that the educational robotics workshops performed in Y3 used a wider variety of robotics kits compared to the educational robotics workshops performed in Y1 and Y2. A new robotics kit introduced in Y3 was Robotic Arm Kit - CBIS Education, which was used to demonstrate mathematical concepts for coordination systems in 2D and 3D space and to demonstrate the application of robotics for solving real-life problems (more specifically, waste disposal and recycling). That fits well with the ER4STEM principle to use educational robotics in order to support the teaching of principles from a variety of domains.

Based on the experience gained from Y1 in September 2016 at the beginning of Y2 during the project Y1 review meeting in Malta, the ER4STEM project partners agreed on using 21st century skills as a unit to encompass industry skills and soft-skills. Moreover, it was decided to develop a unit within the Framework on 21st century skills, which is sub-divided into section on teamwork and collaboration, communication, creativity and critical thinking. Those directions were further developed in Y3. In Y3 the educational robotics workshops curriculum was mostly connected to six of them, namely teamwork and collaboration, mixed gender teams; communication; creativity; critical thinking and evidence of learning as those six skills were among the most frequently targeted by the ER4STEM partners' Y3 activity plans.

Figure 13 Share of all Year 3 workshops that cover the Y2 recommendations in terms of 21st century skills

Source: educational robotics workshops planning, monitoring and control tool.

All data in this section is based on the information obtained from the workshop information forms provided by the project partners, with the exception of the information, related to the students' satisfaction from the workshops (obtained through post-workshop questionnaires).

Some of the indicators **could have different values** when they are reported in Section 4 ER4STEM Workshops Progress Review and in Deliverable 6.3, since the data in those reports is based on data obtained only from students, who provided written consent forms and other evaluation artefacts, while in this report, we analyse the data, provided by the tutors on the overall workshop participation. One should take into account that not all students that had signed written consent forms participated in the workshops and that there were students that had not signed written consent forms but participated in the workshops.

5 CONCLUSION / OUTLOOK

During the third year of the execution phase of the project, the partners were able to successfully design, implement and evaluate 72 educational robotics workshops with 1676 participants in six countries, while implementing key improvements, such as:

- Modifying the educational robotics workshops' delivery process in order to take into account STEM related curricula and involve local teachers and tutors.
- One new educational robotics technology was introduced within 3 workshops carried out within the third project year.
- Use of improved Activity Plans including activity blocks to facilitate the understanding and implementation of a workshop.
- Introduction of improved evaluation methods and tools.
- Focus on 21st century skills and on the ER4STEM values.

During the third project year, the ER4STEM team was able to achieve and even exceed by 7% the total number of students that were planned to be included throughout the whole project. Based on that fact, we can conclude that the WP2 Educational Robotics Workshops was successfully completed.

In this last year of the project we managed to adapt the educational robotics workshops implementation process in order to change its focus from implementation by project partners to initiation and implementation by educators, teachers and researchers.

Moreover, we systemized ER4STEM generic curricula on meso and macro level in order to facilitate and foster the use of the ER4STEM expertise by the target audience. The curriculum is well linked to the ER4STEM Framework and is being integrated within the ER4STEM repository.

The ER4STEM curricula developed throughout the entire project lifecycle and documented in D2.1, D2.2 and D2.3 (this deliverable) will be finalized, summarised and improved as visualization and description in D2.4 ER4STEM Curricula.

6 GLOSSARY / ABBREVIATIONS

AcrossLimits, AL	AcrossLimits, Malta
CU	Cardiff University, UK
EC	European Commission
ER	Educational Robotics
ER4STEM	Educational Robotics for Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
ERW(s)	Educational Robotics Workshop(s)
ESI CEE	European Software Institute - Center Eastern Europe, Bulgaria
Implementation Team	All members of the team that implements the workshop including but not limited to facilitators, teachers, researchers, evaluators and others.
PRIA	Practical Robotics Institute Austria, Austria
Curriculum map	The curriculum map is the contextual visualization of educational robotics learning opportunities, as organized content into a set of use cases and contexts, revolving around desired learning outcomes. It is a part of the context layer of the generic educational robotics curriculum under the ER4STEM project.
Desired learning outcomes	Desired learning outcomes, as understood by the ER4STEM generic curriculum implementation team, lay out what an educator is aiming to convey to students through the educational robotics activity. The term is used in reference to what a student has been able to practice and could be able to transfer to other domains or spheres of life, during and after the end of an educational robotics session, activity or curriculum path, as planned by the educator.
Learning path / Curriculum path	A tool introduced under the ER4STEM project to address desired learning outcomes through a set of use cases. A learning path consists of a set of educational robotics workshops or single activities within the workshops activity plans, which are suitable for a given context, students, specific objectives and prior knowledge. A learning path is designed to be further modified by the educator to fit their specific learning context.
Local teacher/tutor or scientists	Teacher/tutor or scientists from hosting organizations, school or club.
REA	Research Executive Agency
Relevant Stakeholder	A stakeholder that is involvement in specific ERWs activities.
STE(A)M	Science, Technology, Engineering, Art, and Mathematics
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
TUWien	Vienna University of Technology, Austria
UoA	University of Athens, Educational Technology Lab, Greece

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APPENDIX 1 QUANTITATIVE DATA FROM THE ERWS BASED ON THE WORKSHOP INFORMATION FORMS

ERW No	Code	Partner name	Dates from	Dates to	Number of sessions	Number of lead tutors	Number of other tutors/mentors	Age of students from	Age of students to	Total number of students	Number of male students	Number of female students	Group size from	Group size to	Total number of groups	Robotics kits used	Programming languages used
1	AL-2-11-VER3	AccrossLimits	9/6/2017	9/7/2017	2	2	1	11	13	19	12	7	2	3	0	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
2	AL-2-12-VER4	AccrossLimits	9/12/2017	9/13/2017	2	2	1	11	12	20	10	10	2	2	10	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
3	AL-2-13-StCat	AccrossLimits	10/9/2017	10/10/2017	2	2	0	10	12	23	10	13	2	3	10	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
4	AL-2-14-StCat	AccrossLimits	10/16/2017	10/17/2017	2	2	0	10	12	23	9	14	2	3	10	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
5	AL-3-7-QSI-Class1	AccrossLimits	6/5/2018	6/5/2018	1	2	0	9	10	11	7	4	2	3	5	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
6	AL-3-5-StJosephSliemaJuniors	AccrossLimits	5/14/2018	5/14/2018	1	2	0	9	10	25	0	25	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
7	AL-3-9-OutOfClass-2	AccrossLimits	5/26/2018	5/26/2018	1	2	0	9	12	12	9	3	2	2	3	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
8	AL-3-10-St.Dorothy-Year5-1	AccrossLimits	5/29/2018	5/29/2018	1	2	0	9	10	25	0	25	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
9	AL-3-11-St.Dorothy-Year4-1	AccrossLimits	5/31/2018	5/31/2018	1	2	1	8	9	24	0	24	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
10	AL-3-6-StJosephSliemaJuniors	AccrossLimits	5/15/2018	5/15/2018	1	2	0	9	10	26	0	26	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals

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11	AL-3-12-St.Dorothy-Year6-1	AccrossLimits	6/4/2018	6/4/2018	1	3	0	10	12	25	0	25	2	3	11	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
12	AL-3-13-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class1	AccrossLimits	5/28/2018	5/28/2018	1	2	0	6	7	13	5	8	2	3	6	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
13	AL-3-14-LijaPrimary-Year2-Class2_3	AccrossLimits	5/30/2018	5/30/2018	1	2	0	6	7	23	13	10	2	4	10	Dash and Dot	Drag and Drop Visuals
14	PRW2-3-125-3a	ESICEE	2/20/2018	2/27/2018	2	2	1	9	10	27	9	18	3	4	7	Arduino	Scratch
15	PRW2-3-125-3b	ESICEE	3/7/2018	3/12/2018	2	2	0	9	10	24	15	9	3	4	6	Arduino	Scratch
16	PRW2-3-125-3d	ESICEE	3/20/2018	3/27/2018	2	2	0	9	10	28	15	13	3	4	7	Arduino	Scratch
17	PRW2-3-125-3e	ESICEE	3/19/2018	3/26/2018	2	2	0	8	10	28	13	15	3	4	7	Arduino	Scratch
18	PRW2-3-125-3g	ESICEE	2/27/2018	3/6/2018	2	1	0	8	10	26	11	15	2	4	6	Arduino	Scratch
19	PRW2-3-125-3v	ESICEE	2/20/2018	2/27/2018	2	1	1	9	10	28	13	15	3	4	7	Arduino	Scratch
20	PRW2-3-125-4a	ESICEE	10/2/2017	10/9/2017	2	1	2	9	10	26	13	13	2	4	7	Finch	Scratch
21	PRW2-3-125-4b	ESICEE	10/3/2017	10/10/2017	2	2	3	9	10	28	13	15	2	4	7	Finch	Scratch
22	PRW2-3-125-4d	ESICEE	11/13/2017	11/20/2017	2	1	0	9	11	27	13	14	3	4	7	Finch	Scratch
23	PRW2-3-125-4e	ESICEE	11/14/2017	11/21/2017	2	1	0	9	10	26	15	11	2	5	6	Finch	Scratch
24	PRW2-3-125-4g	ESICEE	10/17/2017	10/24/2017	2	1	1	9	10	28	16	12	4	4	7	Finch	Scratch
25	PRW2-3-125-4v	ESICEE	10/16/2017	10/23/2017	2	1	1	9	10	26	16	10	3	5	6	Finch	Scratch

ERW No	Code	Partner name	Dates from	Dates to	Number of sessions	Number of lead tutors	Number of other tutors/mentors	Age of students from	Age of students to	Total number of students	Number of male students	Number of female students	Group size from	Group size to	Total number of groups	Robotics kits used	Programming languages used
26	PRW2-3-125-5j-Arm	ESICEE	4/23/2018	4/30/2018	2	1	0	10	12	27	22	5	2	5	7	Robotic Arm Kit - CBiS Education	Scratch
27	PRW2-3-125-5z-Arm	ESICEE	5/24/2018	5/28/2018	2	1	0	11	12	27	20	7	3	5	7	Robotic Arm Kit - CBiS Education	Scratch
28	PRW2-3-Kuystendil	ESICEE	5/18/2018	5/18/2018	1	1	0	10	12	20	13	7	4	4	5	Robotic Arm Kit - CBiS Education	Scratch
29	PRIA-3-A2-03-MG	PRIA	10/20/2017	1/8/2018	3	1	0	12	15	24	14	10	2	4	9	Hedgehog	Python
30	PRIA-3-A2-02-MG	PRIA	10/19/2017	1/15/2018	3	1	0	12	15	22	12	10	1	3	10	Hedgehog	Python
31	PRIA-3-A1-03-VA	PRIA	11/7/2017	1/29/2018	3	1	2	7	10	21	14	7	1	3	10	Hedgehog	Python
32	PRIA-3-A2-01-AB	PRIA	10/9/2017	1/15/2018	8	1	2	13	14	18	17	1	1	6	11	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
33	PRIA-3-A2-04-MA	PRIA	11/16/2017	2/1/2018	3	1	2	10	13	26	8	18	2	5	7	Hedgehog	Python
34	PRIA-3-A1-04-VA	PRIA	11/9/2017	4/9/2018	2	1	2	8	11	21	13	8	1	3	0	Hedgehog	Blockly
35	PRIA-3-A2-05-MA	PRIA	11/16/2017	2/1/2018	3	1	2	11	14	25	5	20	2	4	10	Hedgehog	Python
36	PRIA-3-A1-05-KL	PRIA	4/23/2018	5/7/2018	2	1	2	8	10	25	11	14	2	3	10	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms

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37	PRIA-3-A1-02-VV	PRIA	10/5/2017	2/26/2018	3	1	2	8	10	28	12	16	2	3	12	Hedgehog	Blockly
38	PRIA-3-A3-01-ECERWS	PRIA	1/22/2018	1/23/2018	2	1	2	13	18	55	48	7	2	9	10	Botball: Wallaby controller	C/C++/Arduino
39	PRIA-3-A1-01-VV	PRIA	9/28/2017	1/26/2018	3	2	3	8	11	18	12	6	1	3	9	Hedgehog	Blockly
40	TU_RoboticClub_2018	TUWien	2/26/2018	5/28/2018	10	0	0	6	11	10	6	4	1	2	6	Thymio II	ASEBA
41	TUW_050318_Workshop_20180305	TUWien	3/5/2018	3/12/2018	2	1	0	18	18	13	13	0	2	3	5	Thymio II	Blockly
42	TUW_060418_Workshop_20180406	TUWien	4/6/2018	4/13/2018	2	1	0	9	12	18	8	10	2	3	9	Thymio II	Thymio VPL
43	TUW_100418_Workshop_20180410	TUWien	4/10/2018	4/24/2018	3	2	0	14	18	25	14	11	2	5	9	Thymio II	Thymio VPL
44	TUW_110418_Workshop_20180411	TUWien	4/11/2018	4/25/2018	3	3	0	14	16	28	16	12	2	5	10	Thymio II	Thymio VPL
45	TUW_140218_Workshop_20180214	TUWien	2/14/2018	2/15/2018	2	1	0	7	9	25	13	12	2	4	9	Thymio II	Blockly
46	TUW_140318_Workshop_20180314	TUWien	3/14/2018	3/15/2018	2	1	0	8	9	23	11	12	2	4	10	Thymio II	Blockly

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47	TUW_190318_Workshop_20180319	TUWien	3/19/2018	3/23/2018	2	1	0	8	9	19	12	7	2	3	9	Thymio II	Blockly
48	TUW_220218_Workshop_20180222	TUWien	2/22/2018	2/23/2018	2	1	0	7	9	25	10	15	2	4	10	Thymio II	Blockly
49	TUW_250418_Workshop_20180425	TUWien	4/25/2018	4/26/2018	2	1	0	6	10	22	10	12	2	4	10	Thymio II	Thymio VPL
50	TUWien-ITA-2017	TUWien	12/22/2017	12/22/2017	1	1	1	14	15	24	13	11	1	3	10	Thymio II	Text programming
51	631_MIHS_1	CU	9/11/2017	10/24/2017	6	2	1	13	14	23	14	9	1	3	0	SLurtle	Scratch
52	631_MIHS_1b	CU	11/6/2017	12/12/2017	6	3	2	13	14	23	14	9	1	3	0	SLurtle	Scratch
53	631_MIHS_2	CU	1/15/2018	2/6/2018	6	4	3	13	14	29	15	14	1	2	15	SLurtle	Scratch
54	631_MIHS_2b	CU	2/19/2018	3/26/2018	6	5	4	13	14	29	15	14	1	2	0	SLurtle	Scratch
55	631_MIHS_3	CU	4/23/2018	5/22/2018	6	6	5	13	14	32	17	15	0	0	-1	SLurtle	ICT/CS
56	631_MIHS_3b	CU	6/4/2018	7/10/2018	6	7	6	2	14	32	17	15	0	0	0	SLurtle	ICT/CS
57	632_MIHS_1	CU	9/11/2017	10/24/2017	6	8	7	13	14	22	9	13	2	2	0	SLurtle	Scratch
58	632_MIHS_1b	CU	11/6/2017	12/12/2017	6	9	8	13	14	22	9	13	2	2	0	SLurtle	Scratch
59	632_MIHS_2	CU	1/15/2018	2/6/2018	6	10	9	13	14	24	10	14	0	0	-1	SLurtle	Scratch
60	632_MIHS_2b	CU	2/11/2018	3/26/2018	6	11	10	13	14	24	10	14	0	0	-1	SLurtle	Scratch
61	633_PYD_1	CU	11/16/2017	12/14/2017	3	12	11	13	14	29	15	14	1	1	27	SLurtle	Scratch

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62	632_MIHS_3	CU	4/23/2018	5/22/2018	6	11	10	13	14	31	17	14	0	0	0	SLurtle	ICT/CS
63	632_MIHS_3b	CU	6/4/2018	7/10/2018	6	12	11	13	14	31	17	14	0	0	0	SLurtle	ICT/CS
64	UoA 437	UoA	2/27/2018	3/1/2018	3	3	1	16	17	11	11	0	2	5	3	Arduino	C/C++/Arduino
65	UoA 434b	UoA	3/13/2018	4/17/2018	4	4	2	14	17	15	11	4	1	3	5	Arduino	C/C++/Arduino
66	UoA 434a	UoA	2/1/2018	3/8/2018	5	5	3	14	15	15	7	8	1	3	5	Arduino	C/C++/Arduino
67	UoA 432	UoA	12/18/2017	12/22/2017	3	6	4	11	11	18	10	8	4	5	4	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
68	UoA 431	UoA	3/15/2018	3/30/2018	3	7	5	10	10	13	6	7	1	5	4	LEGO WeDo	Scratch
69	UoA 438	UoA	12/16/2017	12/17/2017	3	8	6	11	15	21	12	9	0	0	0	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
70	UoA 436	UoA	4/25/2018	5/22/2018	4	9	7	10	11	22	11	11	3	4	6	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
71	UoA 435	UoA	2/19/2018	3/2/2018	3	10	8	6	13	13	12	1	2	3	5	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms
72	UoA 433	UoA	1/27/2018	2/10/2018	3	11	9	10	15	17	10	7	2	4	5	LEGO Mindstorms	LEGO Mindstorms

